

Allosteric Antibody Modulation of EGFR Activity: Bridging Experiment and *In Silico* Modeling [☆]

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Abstract

Allosteric regulation provides a powerful framework for modulating receptor signaling in both physiological and therapeutic contexts. The epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR), a receptor tyrosine kinase frequently dysregulated in cancer, undergoes activation through conformational transitions that couple extracellular ligand binding to intracellular kinase signaling. Here, we explore how camelid derived VHH (variable domain of the heavy chain of a heavy chain-only)-antibodies can exploit this allosteric architecture to inhibit EGFR function. Using a panel of single domain monospecific and biparatopic antibodies, targeting non-overlapping EGFR epitopes, we combined experimental assays with structure-based modeling to dissect their effects on EGFR signaling and internalization. AlphaFold3-predicted EGFR–antibody complexes were analyzed using the Structure-Based Statistical Mechanical Model of Allostery (SBSMMA) to compute residue-level allosteric modulations induced upon binding. The resulting profiles revealed that only a subset of epitope combinations produced long-range allosteric responses reaching the juxtamembrane segment and the kinase domain. These patterns correlated with effective inhibition of downstream ERK and AKT signaling in cellular assays. In contrast, some constructs with high internalization capacity induced minimal allosteric propagation and weak signaling suppression, indicating a mechanistic decoupling of receptor uptake from conformational regulation. Together, these results define distinct allosteric modes of EGFR modulation by VHH-antibodies and show how computational modeling based on energetic propagation can complement experimental screening to guide the design of next-generation allosteric biologics.

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Introduction

By transmitting functional effects through conformational or energetic coupling between distant sites, nature has found in allostery a powerful means of regulating protein function [1–3]. Traditionally associated with enzymes and

small-molecule binding, allostery is increasingly recognized as a fundamental mechanism of action for biologics, including antibodies [4,5]. While most therapeutic antibodies act by sterically blocking ligand binding or receptor dimerization, growing evidence shows that antibodies can also engage allosteric sites to modulate receptor function at a distance. In a recent review, we outlined the conceptual and mechanistic foundations of allosteric

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antibodies and proposed a framework for their rational discovery and design [6].

EGFR, the epidermal growth factor receptor, is a receptor tyrosine kinase (RTK) that exemplifies how dynamic conformational transitions govern signaling output. In its resting state, EGFR adopts a tethered conformation that autoinhibits dimerization. Ligand binding to extracellular domains I and III induces a structural rearrangement, exposing the dimerization arm in domain II and enabling receptor dimerization and activation of the intracellular kinase domain. This process is tightly regulated in healthy cells but frequently dysregulated in cancer through EGFR overexpression, mutation, or aberrant recycling [7].

Approved anti-EGFR monoclonal antibodies, such as cetuximab [8] and panitumumab [9], primarily act by blocking ligand access to domain III. However, resistance mutations in the ligand-binding site, along with incomplete inhibition of downstream signaling, have limited their long-term efficacy [7]. Structural and computational studies have revealed that EGFR activation involves coordinated conformational shifts extending from the extracellular domains through the transmembrane helix to the intracellular juxtamembrane segment and kinase module [10,11]. This distributed architecture makes EGFR an ideal candidate for allosteric modulation, where conformational effects at one site can propagate to control function at another (see Figure 1 for an illustration).

Combinations of non-competing antibodies have been explored to enhance EGFR inhibition, particularly by targeting non-overlapping epitopes [12–14]. Biparatopic antibodies (BpAbs) extend this logic by encoding two binding specificities into a single molecule, allowing simultaneous engagement of distinct epitopes on the same receptor. BpAbs have been shown to enhance avidity, alter receptor trafficking, promote clustering, or modulate signaling pathways [15]. A notable example is zanidatamab, a biparatopic anti-HER2 antibody approved for HER2-positive biliary tract cancer [16]. Several BpAbs targeting EGFR have demonstrated potent downregulation in preclinical studies [17–19], yet none have advanced to clinical trials. This gap may stem from a limited understanding of the conformational and allosteric effects induced by specific epitope combinations.

We recently identified a set of VHs targeting four distinct allosterically sensitive regions of EGFR [20,21]. In the present study, we engineer biparatopic constructs from these single domain antibodies (sdAb) and systematically evaluate their capacity to modulate EGFR function through allosteric mechanisms. We combine AlphaFold3-predicted models [22,23] with the structure-based statistical mechanical model of allostery (SBSMMA) to simulate the energetic consequences of single and dual epitope engagement [24–27]. These *in silico* predictions are then compared with experimental measurements of

EGFR signaling inhibition and receptor internalization.

Our findings show that epitope pairing governs not only binding and avidity, but also the propagation of mechanical strain into intracellular regulatory regions, with clear consequences for signaling output. Some biparatopics, such as those combining domain IV and domain II epitopes, achieve strong allosteric activation of the juxtamembrane segment and kinase C-lobe, correlating with potent ERK and AKT pathway inhibition. Others, despite high binding affinity or internalization, fail to engage the allosteric network effectively. This work provides mechanistic insight into how antibody format and epitope selection shape functional responses and supports the rational design of allosteric antibodies for targeting conformationally regulated receptors like EGFR.

Material and Methods

AlphaFold3 structure prediction of EGFR–VHH complexes

The AlphaFold3 webserver [23] was used to generate structural models of each VHH in complex with the extracellular region of human EGFR. To assess both epitope locations and potential off-target interactions, each VHH was modeled against multiple EGFR fragments. These included the full extracellular domain (residues 1–614), paired domains (EGFR_I_II, EGFR_II_III, and EGFR_III_IV), and epitope-spanning subsets, such as EGFR_294_543 (including domains II–III–IV) and EGFR_1_294 (covering domains I–II) as they resulted from the BLI assays. For each VHH–EGFR combination, five structural models were generated per seed for a total number of 145 predictions (29 seeds in total). Model confidence was evaluated using standard AlphaFold3 metrics: the interface TM-score (ipTM), global predicted TM-score (pTM), model ranking score, predicted fraction of disordered residues, and cross-interface predicted alignment error (PAE). A full summary of AlphaFold3 model confidence across all domain pairings is provided in Supplementary Table S2.

Allosteric modeling with AlloSigMA

To evaluate allosteric communication in EGFR, we applied the Structure-Based Statistical Mechanical Model of Allostery (SBSMMA) [24,26,28], which is implemented in the AlloSigMA web server and in standalone version [25,27], and widely used to compile the AlloMAPs databases of allosteric proteins, [29,30]. Representing the protein as a harmonic network of C α atoms, the SBSMMA computes the conformational free energy changes induced by local perturbations such as ligand binding or mutations, which are modeled as localized perturbations to contact stiffness. The goal is to quantify how binding events at specific sites

Figure 1. Conceptual model of EGFR modulation by antibodies. (A) Monomeric EGFR in the tethered, autoinhibited conformation. Binding of an antibody to extracellular allosteric epitopes (for instance, on domains I or III) can induce conformational or energetic changes that propagate through the transmembrane helix (TMH), juxtamembrane segment (JMS), and into the kinase domain, modulating activity at a distance. (B) Ligand-bound EGFR in the extended, dimerization-competent state. Antibodies binding to overlapping sites with the ligand (e.g., domain III) act primarily through steric blockade or dimerization interference. The work investigates how single and biparotopic antibodies differentially exploit these mechanisms to control EGFR signaling.

reshape the energetic landscape throughout the structure. The harmonic energy function in the unperturbed (reference) state is defined as

$$E^{(0)}(r - r^0) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i,j} K_{ij} (d_{ij} - d_{ij}^0)^2$$

where d_{ij} is the distance between residues i and j in the current structure, d_{ij}^0 is the reference distance in the unperturbed structure, K_{ij} is a distance-dependent spring constant, and the sum runs over residue pairs within a 25 Å cutoff. Perturbations such as ligand binding, are introduced increasing the spring constants among residues within the binding site, mimicking local stiffening. The perturbed harmonic energy is

$$E^{(P)}(r - r^0, S) = E^{(0)}(r - r^0) + \frac{\alpha}{2} \sum_{i,j \in S} K_{ij} (d_{ij} - d_{ij}^0)^2$$

where S is the set of perturbed residue pairs, and $\alpha \gg 1$ is the stiffening factor, which is typically $\sim 10^2$. The harmonic network is diagonalized to compute low-frequency normal modes, which approximate collective motions in the near-equilibrium regime. Each mode μ is associated with a displacement vector $e_{i,\mu}$ and variance σ^2 . The elastic potential experienced by a residue i from the motion of its neighbors is given by

$U_i = 1/2 \sum_{\mu} \varepsilon_{\mu,i} \sigma_{\mu}^2$, where $\varepsilon_{\mu,i} = \sum_j |e_{\mu,i} - e_{\mu,j}|^2$, which quantifies the total deformation around residue i . For a given residue, the free energy change in the bound/perturbed state is computed as

$$\Delta g_{\text{residue}} = \frac{1}{2} k_B T \sum_{\mu} \log \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{\mu,\text{residue}}^{(\text{bound})}}{\varepsilon_{\mu,\text{residue}}^{(\text{free})}} \right)$$

The allosteric effects are then quantified via the allosteric modulation $\Delta h_{\text{residue}}$, defined as the background-free change in elastic work exerted on residue upon perturbation. Formally, $\Delta h_{\text{residue}}$ is obtained by subtracting the chain-average free energy change $\langle \Delta g \rangle_{\text{chain}}$ from the per-residue background-free energy response

$$\Delta h_{\text{residue}} = \Delta g_{\text{residue}} - \langle \Delta g \rangle_{\text{chain}}$$

Ligand binding is simulated by increasing the coupling strength within the perturbed site, and mutations (not used in this work) are modeled by scaling the interactions of a residue with its neighbors [26]. The calculation uses the lowest-frequency normal modes to approximate conformational ensembles, and the $\Delta h_{\text{residue}}$ values reflect the energetic response across the protein structure devoid of background effects.

In this work binding was simulated as a local perturbation to contact stiffness using residues within 8 Å of the VHH interface (from AlphaFold3 models). For each VHH–EGFR complex, five AlphaFold3-predicted models were used as independent input structures. SBSMMA was run on each model separately, and Δh values were averaged across the ensemble to obtain robust, representative allosteric profiles. Error ribbons in the Δh plots reflect the standard deviation across models and provide a built-in estimate of model-dependent variability. This ensemble-based approach, while coarse-grained, offers a thermodynamically grounded and computationally efficient method for mapping long-range allosteric responses. It is particularly suited for large-scale screening of antibody–receptor complex interactions, where atomistic methods based for instance on molecular dynamics, would be computationally prohibitive. The method captures domain-level communication patterns and has been previously applied to study mutation effects, ligand-induced modulation, and regulatory coupling in signaling proteins across different structural contexts [2,29,30].

All profiles reported here were computed using the AlloSigMA standalone package. While the default number of modes is 10, we systematically tested 10, 20, and 30 modes and observed qualitatively similar Δh profiles across the range. For all reported results, 20 modes were used to enhance spatial resolution while preserving consistency across perturbations as we previously observed elsewhere [24].

Cell lines and protein reagents

MDA-MB-468 cells (ATCC) were cultured in RPMI media supplemented with 10% fetal bovine serum, 1% glutamine and 1% sodium pyruvate at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂. Expi293F cells were obtained from ThermoFisher Scientific and were cultured in a serum-free expression media under agitation at 37 °C in a humidified atmosphere containing 5% CO₂.

Recombinant human (rh) his-tagged epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) extracellular domain (amino acids: 25–642) was produced by Merck Healthcare KGaA.

AlexaFluor[®] 488 AffiniPure™ Fab Fragment Goat anti-human IgG, Fc_γ fragment specific was purchased from Jackson ImmunoResearch (109-547-008).

Cloning, expression, and purification of DuoBody[®]

Anti-EGFR binders were reformatted as DuoBody[®] with either the F405L or the K409R mutations in a pTT5 vector by Geneart (ThermoFisher Scientific).

Recombinant transient antibody expression was conducted in Expi293F cells following manufacturer's instructions (ThermoFisher Scientific). Six days post transfection, cells were harvested, and antibody purified from the supernatant using MabSelect antibody purification chromatography resin (GE Healthcare). Samples were formulated in PBS (Sigma Aldrich), and concentrations determined using QIA expert system (Qiagen). Purity was assessed by size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) analysis.

Generation of biparatopic antibodies

Biparatopic antibodies were generated by controlled Fab-arm exchange (cFAE) according to an optimized protocol described by Barron and colleagues [31]. Briefly, parental DuoBody[®] molecule concentrations were first normalized to 14 μM and combined in a 1:1 M ratio. Subsequently, a 20-fold molar excess of tris(2-carboxyethyl) phosphine (Sigma Aldrich) was added to the samples for six hours. Afterwards, a 40-molar excess of PEG-azide (Sigma Aldrich) was added for quenching. Samples were reoxidized after an incubation of six days at room temperature.

BLI binding assays

All the experiments have been performed using the Octet RED[®] BLI system (Sartorius) according to the manufacturer's guidelines at 25 °C with 1000 rpm agitation. Relevant controls were included for each experiment (e.g., unloaded biosensor or unrelated antigen).

For initial qualitative binding assay, DuoBody[®] molecules were loaded onto anti-human IgG Fc capture (AHC2) biosensors for 180 s (5 μg/mL), after a 60 s baseline step in kinetic buffer (KB; PBS + 0.1% Tween 20 + 1% BSA) association to rhEGFR was tested for 180 s followed by a dissociation step in KB for 180 s.

For kinetic analysis, biparatopic antibodies were loaded on AHC2 biosensors at a high concentration (15 μg/mL). After a rinsing step in KB, an association step with decreasing concentrations of the EGFR was measured for 300 s followed by a dissociation step for 600 s in KB. Data were analyzed using Sartorius analysis software.

Internalization assay

To evaluate the impact of the biparatopic antibodies on EGFR internalization, a flow cytometry assay described by Li and colleagues was followed [32]. MDA-MB-468 cells were incubated with biparatopic antibodies or parental molecules on ice for 1 h, followed by two washing steps to remove unbound antibodies. Control cells remained on ice and the rest of the cells were incubated at 37 °C for 4 h. Afterwards, cells were fixed in

2% paraformaldehyde for 20 min at room temperature. Then, cells were incubated with AlexaFluor[®]488 anti-human Fc for 30 min in the dark. After two washing steps, cells were resuspended in PBS + 1% BSA + 20 μ g/mL of propidium iodide (Invitrogen). Internalization was measured by FACS on an iQue3 VBR (Sartorius) and GraphPad was used to plot the data. Receptor-antibody internalization was calculated as percentage mean fluorescent intensity (MFI) loss at 37 °C relative to that on ice.

MAPK/ERK signaling pathway

A cell line reporter assay using luciferase (SRE Reporter – HEK293 Cell line, BPS Bioscience) was performed to evaluate the impact of the antibodies on the MAPK/ERK signaling pathway in the same conditions that we previously described [20]. The luminescence was measured using a Synergy Neo2 (BioTek).

AKT/PI3K signaling pathway

The Phospho-AKT1/2/3 (ser473) HTRF kit (64AKSPEG, Revvity) was used to evaluate the inhibition of the AKT/PI3K signaling pathways. 3.5×10^4 MDA-MB-468 cells were seeded onto a bottom-clear 96-well culture plate and incubated overnight for adherence. The next day, the medium was removed, and cells were serum-starved overnight. The next day, cells were pretreated with the respective BpAbs for 1 h at 37 °C before stimulation with 20 ng/mL of EGFR for 10 min at 37 °C. Afterwards, the medium was removed, and cell lysed. Manufacturer's kit protocol was followed. HTRF measurements were performed using a PHERAstar device (BMG).

Data analysis of the experiments

Graphical and statistical analysis were done with GraphPad Prism 8 software. When required, one-way ANOVA was performed in addition to Dunnett's test. $p \leq 0.05$ were considered as statistically significant.

Results

Structural prediction of VHH–EGFR complexes using AlphaFold3

To elucidate the binding epitopes and potential allosteric mechanisms of selected anti-EGFR VHH antibodies and identifying best combinations for biparatopic combinations, we used AlphaFold3 (AF3) [23] to predict the structure of EGFR in complex with six VHHs: A2, E5, E6, B3, G9, and C1. These clones, were previously yeast surface display (YSD) domain mapped into distinct regions [20]. The YSD mapping revealed that B3 and G9 both recognize domain II, though G9 partially impedes B3 in at least one orientation. A2, E5,

and E6 bind to domain III and were found to compete with matuzumab, a monoclonal antibody that targets a linear epitope within this region [33]. C1, while not fully competitive with any other antibody, partially blocks E5 in some orientations and is thus hypothesized to bind the upper portion of domain II. These domain assignments were used to guide input selection for AlphaFold3 modeling. VHHs targeting domain II (B3, G9) were first modeled with residues 1–294 of EGFR, while those targeting domain III (A2, E5, E6) used residues 294–543. For C1, which bridges both domains, the full extracellular region (1–614) was used for modeling.

For each VHH–EGFR complex, AlphaFold3 predictions were generated using the AlphaFold3 web server [23]. Each job associated with a seed returned five ranked structural models per VHH–EGFR pairing. EGFR residues within 8 Å of each VHH were identified as contact residues (see Supplementary Table S1). Predicted complexes were aligned to the tethered monomeric EGFR structure previously described by Arkhipov et al. [34], and representative models are shown in Figure 2, with EGFR domains and VHHs color-coded. Model confidence was assessed using standard AlphaFold3 metrics, including the interface TM-score (ipTM), global pTM, model ranking score, fraction of predicted disordered residues, and the mean cross-interface predicted alignment error (pae_cross), the results are shown in the Supplementary Table S2 (EGFR portion column highlighted in green). VHHs E6, G9, and C1 showed consistently high ipTM values (mean > 0.80) and low cross-interface predicted alignment error (pae_cross < 2.5 Å) when modeled against epitope-matched EGFR fragments (EGFR_294_543 or full-length ECD), indicating robust interface prediction and precise VHH placement. In contrast, A2, B3, and E5 exhibited low ipTM scores (~ 0.11) and elevated pae_cross values (~ 15 – 16 Å) across their five models, indicative of limited interface confidence. These low-confidence metrics likely reflect, in part, the absence of close sequence homology to these VHHs in AlphaFold3's training and alignment databases, reducing the quality of paired MSA signals required for confident multimer predictions.

As a control, AlphaFold3 predictions were also generated for all VHHs in complex with the full extracellular domain (ECD) of EGFR (except for C1, where the full ECD was already used in the main analysis), as well as with contiguous domain pairs (EGFR_I_II, EGFR_II_III, EGFR_III_IV). For E6, G9, and C1, the epitope-guided models (EGFR_294_543, EGFR_1_294, and EGFR full, respectively) yielded the best interface confidence metrics (ipTM > 0.80, PAE_cross < 2.5 Å), supporting their use for allosteric analysis. For A2, B3, and E5, the alternative domain combinations generally produced comparable ipTM and PAE_cross scores to the epitope-mapped models (see Supplementary Table S2). Notably, only E5

Figure 2. Structural models of VHH-EGFR complexes used for allosteric analysis. For each VHH nanobody (A2, E5, E6, G9, B3, C1), five AlphaFold3 structural models of the tethered EGFR monomer bound to the VHH are shown (panels A–F). The bound VHHs are depicted in color and overlaid to highlight positional and orientational variability across the ensemble, particularly notable for A2, E5, and B3. EGFR is shown in gray, with domain architecture preserved: extracellular domains I–IV, transmembrane helix (TMH), juxtamembrane segment (JMS), and kinase domain. These five structural predictions per VHH were used as input for SBSMMA calculations. Δh responses were computed for each model individually and averaged across the ensemble. This multi-conformer approach accounts for structural heterogeneity aimed at obtaining final profiles reflecting consistent rather than model-specific effects.

showed a modest improvement in interface confidence with the EGFR_III_IV model, though this did not alter the qualitative binding pose. To ensure interpretability and consistency, we adopted a modeling strategy rooted in epitope mapping, selecting for each VHH the EGFR fragment that best matched experimental evidence – except for C1, which lacked mapping data and was modeled against full EGFR. SBSMMA analysis was performed individually on each of the five AlphaFold3-predicted complexes per VHH, using the selected fragment, and the resulting Δh profiles were averaged to generate a robust and representative allosteric map. In all cases, the predicted models exhibited consistent backbone conformations, low disorder, and no steric clashes.

These findings suggest that while all models are suitable for identifying general binding regions, interpretation of atomic-level details, such as side-chain complementarity or hydrogen bonding networks, should be approached with care, particularly for models with lower ipTM scores and elevated cross-interface PAE values. Such predictions may reflect uncertainty or hallucination of interface geometry, especially in the absence of structural templates or co-evolutionary signal. This limitation reflects a broader challenge in the field: predicting antibody–antigen interfaces is inherently difficult, especially when involving flexible or discontinuous epitopes, more generally because of high flexibility of antibody CDR loops. However, generating multiple structural models, as proposed here with at least five independent predictions per

complex, provides a useful way to capture alternative binding modes and interface topologies across the ensemble. Our objective was not to extract detailed atomic interactions, but to characterize the approximate binding sites and evaluate their potential to induce long-range allosteric effects using the SBSMMA, a method that integrates global structural features and is relatively insensitive to fine-grained interfacial noise. Recent systematic assessments have shown that although AlphaFold-based approaches may not yet fully resolve antibody–antigen interactions at atomic resolution, they can reliably suggest binding regions and interface topologies when used with ensemble predictions [35,36]. To assess the estimated binding modes, we compared VHH contact residues to known interfaces of the native ligand EGF (domains I and III) and therapeutic antibodies cetuximab and matuzumab (both targeting domain III), which are shown in the Supplemental Table S1. Finally, all predicted AlphaFold3 complexes used in this work are available as Supplementary Dataset on Figshare [37].

Domain II binders: B3 and G9. Both B3 and G9 bind to domain II of EGFR, as previously indicated by epitope mapping and competition assays. Their AF3-predicted epitopes are distinct in spatial distribution and residue usage. B3 engages surface spanning residues 13 to 210, involving multiple loops and β -strands. In several models, B3 also contacts domain I residues such as 13 to 19, 68, 98, 99, and 128. Many of these are also part of the EGF domain I interface, suggesting that B3 may mimic EGF binding in this region.

In contrast, G9 binds a topologically distinct epitope centered within residues 144–239. This interface is primarily located in the distal region of domain II and does not overlap with EGF contact residues, implying a likely non-competitive or allosteric mode of action. The differences in binding footprint support the experimental observation that B3 and G9 do not compete and can be combined in biparatopic formats.

Domain III binders: A2, E5, and E6. The VHs A2, E5, and E6 engage domain III of EGFR, overlapping with or adjacent to the known binding site of matuzumab, which spans residues 433 to 466. Despite this common region, each antibody exhibits distinct binding orientation and residue coverage in AF3 models.

A2 interacts consistently with residues from 294 to 538, with convergence on the region from 454 to 460, strongly overlapping matuzumab's epitope. Additional recurrent contacts include residues 428–430, 455–459, and an extended region from 500 to 530. A2 does not show overlap with the cetuximab binding site, which is located further N-terminal, between residues 349 and 468.

E5 exhibits two alternative binding modes across the five AF3 predictions. In four models, the binding interface spans residues 348–468, encompassing multiple residues shared with both the EGF and cetuximab epitopes, such as 384, 409, 417, 440, 441, 467, and 468. In one model, however, E5 shifts toward a distinct interface between residues 476 and 494, suggesting potential flexibility in binding orientation or alternative epitope accessibility.

E6 binds across the interface from 294 to 534, covering extensive portions of both domain II and domain III. It shares key residues with matuzumab (particularly 454–460) and also engages residues that are part of the EGF and cetuximab sites, especially those between 417 and 441. The predicted contacts suggest that E6 uses CDR2 and CDR3 to achieve a hybrid binding mode spanning multiple structural elements.

Although A2, E5, and E6 each show notable overlap with residues in the cetuximab epitope, none of these antibodies compete with cetuximab in experimental assays. This apparent discrepancy can be reconciled by the fact that structural overlap of contact residues does not necessarily translate to steric competition [38]. These VHs likely bind in orientations that allow co-engagement or occupy peripheral regions of the cetuximab interface. Additionally, cetuximab's binding involves not only specific residues but also conformational loop stabilization. VHs may not disrupt these features, allowing simultaneous binding.

C1 as multidomain binder. The C1 VHH was modeled using the full extracellular region of EGFR (residues 1–621) to resolve its ambiguous epitope. While C1 does not directly compete with E5, AF3 predictions show a convergent binding site that spans domains II, III, and IV. The predicted contact residues fall primarily in the regions from 247 to 297 and from 526 to 579. Although C1 does not significantly overlap with the known binding sites of EGF or therapeutic antibodies, it shares some contact residues with E5 and E6, particularly between 526 and 530. This may explain partial competitive effects observed experimentally. The cross-domain nature of C1's binding suggests a unique conformational influence on EGFR that may contribute to its modulatory activity.

Experimental mapping of competition relationships by BLI

To probe the spatial relationships among the VHH binding sites, we performed pairwise competition assays using biolayer interferometry (Octet). Each VHH, along with the reference antibody matuzumab, was used as a primary binder to saturate EGFR, followed by injection of a second VHH to assess binding compatibility. The second-

phase binding response reflects whether the two antibodies simultaneously engage the receptor, allowing the construction of a competition matrix.

The results, showed in panel A of Figure S1, exhibited two mutually exclusive epitope clusters: one comprising A2, E5, E6, and matuzumab, and another including B3 and G9, which displayed no cross-competition with the first group. Within the A2/E5/E6 cluster, complete competition was observed in all pairwise combinations, consistent with a shared or overlapping epitope centered on domain III, as suggested by AlphaFold3-predicted contact residues and the known matuzumab footprint. In contrast, B3 and G9 did not interfere with any other VHH, supporting their distinct binding to domain II, and their partial competition with each other indicates proximal but non-identical sites.

C1 displayed an intermediate competition profile: while fully blocking A2, it did not interfere with matuzumab and only partially competed with E5 and E6, suggesting only partial epitope overlap with domain III binders. Notably, AlphaFold3 models predict C1 binding across domains II and III, consistent with its ability to interfere with antibodies targeting either region.

Overall, the competition network derived from Octet experiments showed strong concordance with AlphaFold3-modeled epitopes (see panel B in Figure S1), with complete blockers mapping to shared or adjacent regions, and non-competing pairs engaging spatially separated surfaces. This integrative approach allowed us to validate and refine the YSD epitope map used to restrict the structural modeling domain for each VHH.

Computational analysis of allosteric communication in tethered EGFR via SBSMMA

To characterize how different classes of ligands – natural, therapeutic monoclonal antibodies, and novel single domain antibodies (VHHs) modulate the allosteric landscape of EGFR, we employed the Structure-Based Statistical Mechanical Model of Allostery (SBSMMA) [24–27]. This approach uses a harmonic network representation of the protein to model binding as a localized perturbation and evaluates its dynamical consequences in terms of Δh allosteric modulation, which is the change in conformational work exerted on distal sites. A positive Δh reflects increased conformational freedom (softening), whereas a negative Δh indicates local rigidification (see Methods). The model was applied to the complete monomeric tethered EGFR conformation, obtained in the study of Arkhipov et al. [5], which elucidated the architecture of the EGFR receptor and its interactions with the cellular membrane. The EGFR structure encompasses the extracellular domains I–IV, the transmembrane helix (TMH), the juxtamembrane segment (JMS), and the full intracellular kinase module. While the SBSMMA was originally developed for small ligand

perturbations, its formulation naturally generalizes to larger protein interfaces, enabling its application here for the first time to monoclonal antibodies (mAbs) and camelid nanobodies (VHHs). To mitigate the paratope uncertainties in relation to the low-quality complex predictions and still derive significant functional insight, we employed a multiple-conformer approach. The aim is to integrate variability in VHH–EGFR orientation and paratope geometry directly into the Δh profiles, allowing the resulting allosteric maps to reflect model-dependent uncertainty. The standard deviation across the five predictions per VHH is shown as an error ribbon, capturing the spread of Δh values and thus serving as a confidence estimate for the robustness of each response (see Figures 3–5).

Baseline allosteric signatures of EGF and therapeutic antibodies. We first analyzed the effects of EGF binding to domain I (EGF_I), domain III (EGF_III), and both sites simultaneously (EGF_I \times EGF_III). As shown in Figure 3ABC, EGF binding induces weak and spatially confined Δh signals, primarily restricted to the extracellular domains. Despite EGF's essential biological role, its perturbation in the monomeric context fails to propagate appreciable energetic strain into the TMH, JMS, or kinase domain. This suggests that EGF-induced signaling relies predominantly on quaternary transitions such as untethering and dimerization, which are present in the tethered monomeric model and thus not expected to yield strong allosteric signals.

The mAbs cetuximab and matuzumab, which both bind to domain III, similarly produced localized and weak Δh perturbations (Figure 3D–E). Cetuximab, which competitively blocks EGF binding, shares a Δh signature very similar to EGF_III. Matuzumab, although non-competitive, acts by stabilizing the tethered conformation and likewise fails to induce long-range perturbation. Together, these observations define a “low allosteric impact” class of antibodies that modulate EGFR primarily via steric (EGF competitive) or conformational restriction of the ECD, rather than through distal energetic transmission.

Allosteric signatures of VHH-based antibodies. In contrast, camelid derived VHHs targeting diverse epitopes across EGFR elicited a broad spectrum of spatially distributed allosteric responses (Figure 4). Among them:

- C1 binding generated pronounced Δh suppression in domain IV, coupled with enhanced conformational mobility in the JMS, kinase C-lobe, and kinase core, which are hallmarks of strong long-range communication.
- E6 binding, although targeting a distinct site, yielded a similarly potent allosteric signature, with positive Δh spanning intracellular domains.

Figure 3. Allosteric modulation profiles of EGFR upon binding of EGF and therapeutic antibodies. Residue-level Δh profiles calculated using SBSMMA for the tethered EGFR monomer upon binding of: (A) EGF to domain I (EGF_I), (B) EGF to domain III (EGF_III), (C) EGF to both domains I and III simultaneously (EGF_IxEGF_III), (D) cetuximab, and (E) matuzumab. All perturbations were modeled based on experimental binding interfaces. Color-mapped structures illustrate the spatial distribution of Δh modulation, with negative values (red) indicating local rigidification and positive values (blue) reflecting increased conformational flexibility. All five conditions induce only modest and localized allosteric effects, primarily confined to the extracellular region, with limited propagation to the intracellular juxtamembrane segment or kinase domain. The color-mapped representations in Figures 3–5 were obtained with the python package NGLview with a tube-like view and radius scale = 10 [39]. These profiles serve as baseline comparators for the stronger, more distal responses observed with the VHH-based antibodies of this work.

Figure 4. Allosteric modulation of EGFR by individual VHH nanobodies. Residue-level Δh profiles of the tethered EGFR monomer in response to binding of six nanobodies: (A) C1, (B) E8, (C) G9, (D) A2, (E) E5 & (F) B3. For each binder, the perturbation was averaged across five AlphaFold3-predicted EGFR–VHH complex models. Color-mapped EGFR structures show the spatial distribution of Δh values: blue indicates regions with increased conformational mobility (positive Δh), while red indicates rigidification (negative Δh). C1 and E6 exhibit broad allosteric responses extending into the JMS and kinase lobes, whereas B3 and E5 show more localized or weakly propagating effects. These profiles reveal epitope-specific differences in long-range modulation and form the basis for predicting functional synergy in biparatopic combinations.

Figure 5. Allosteric modulation of EGFR by biparatopic nanobody combinations. Residue-level Δh profiles of the tethered EGFR monomer in response to six representative biparatopic nanobody constructs: (A) C1xG9, (B) C1xA2, (C) C1xE6, (D) B3xE6, (E) G9xA2, (F) B3xG9. For each combination, 25 AlphaFold3 models (5×5 pairings) were generated and used to compute ensemble-averaged allosteric responses. Color-mapped structures show Δh values across EGFR, with blue indicating increased flexibility (positive Δh) and red indicating rigidification (negative Δh). C1-based combinations, particularly C1xE6 and C1xA2, show strong distal modulation extending into the JMS and kinase lobes, while combinations like B3xE6 and B3xG9 display weaker or more localized responses. These data highlight the epitope-dependent and cooperative nature of biparatopic allosteric modulation.

- G9, while weaker in distal transmission, showed a bimodal response, with ECD suppression and modest JMS enhancement, which is consistent with its experimental bias toward AKT activation and internalization.

Other VHs (A2, B3, E5) showed intermediate or context-dependent patterns, establishing a diverse landscape of epitope-dependent perturbation modes.

The segment spanning residues 241–261 corresponds to a β -strand within domain II that plays a central structural role in stabilizing the intramolecular tether between domains II and IV of EGFR. This β -strand is part of the interface that locks the receptor in its inactive monomeric conformation. Allosteric modulation in this region is therefore functionally meaningful, as it reflects mechanical disruption or reinforcement of the tethering constraint. Notably, this segment consistently shows strong Δh responses across multiple VHs. C1 induces pronounced rigidification of this β -strand, consistent with stabilization of the tethered state. In contrast, E6, G9, and A2 elicit localized softening, which may correspond to partial unlocking or destabilization of this conformational lock.

Cooperative allosteric transmission in biparatopic VHH combinations. To explore the effects of combinatorial binding, we constructed all pairwise

biparatopic VHH perturbations, sampling all 5×5 unique combinations of AlphaFold3-predicted structures per pair and the Δh responses averaged to obtain a robust consensus profile incorporating binding interface variability. Selected profiles are shown in Figure 5, while the complete set is provided in Figure S2 (Supplementary). According to the SBSMMA, among the combinations, C1xE6 and C1xA2 emerged as the most potent allosteric propagators. These pairs induced deep Δh suppression in domain IV (-2.0 and -2.4 kcal/mol, respectively) and simultaneous positive shifts across the JMS ($+2.0$ kcal/mol) and kinase lobes (up to $+1.7$ kcal/mol), indicating robust long-range coupling from the ECD to the intracellular signaling regions.

Other pairs such as C1xG9 and B3xE6 also triggered distinguishable but more localized allosteric signatures. C1xG9 maintained strong suppression in domain IV, with moderate activation in the kinase C-lobe ($+1.1$ kcal/mol), while B3xE6 exhibited partial transmission through JMS and kinase with milder overall amplitudes. In contrast, combinations like G9xA2, B3xG9, and G9xE6 displayed more diffuse and attenuated perturbation profiles, lacking the coherent transmission pattern observed in the top-performing pairs. Finally, combinations such as G9xE5 and B3xE5 served as non-cooperative controls. These profiles showed limited enhancement compared to their single

components, suggesting weak or absent synergy and supporting a model of non-additive, possibly competing, perturbation effects.

The regional Δh averages underlying these observations are reported in Figure 6B and discussed in the following paragraph. Taken together, these results show that biparatopic binding can substantially reshape EGFR's allosteric landscape for given pairs of VHHs – especially those involving C1 – acting as effective long-range modulators.

A notable feature conserved across this analysis is the modulation of the β -strand spanning residues 241–261 in domain II, a region structurally involved in the tethering interface with domain IV. As observed in the monoparatopic profiles, binders such as C1 induce marked rigidification of this β -strand, while E6, G9, and A2 promote its softening. These mechanical effects are preserved in biparatopic combinations: C1-based pairs (C1xE6, C1xA2) maintain the rigidification signature, whereas combinations like G9xA2 and B3xE6 inherit the softening behavior. This reproducible modulation highlights the β -strand as a sensitive allosteric node and supports its role in coupling external binding events to conformational transitions relevant to EGFR activation.

Global similarity and clustering of allosteric profiles. To obtain a system-level view, we computed the pairwise Pearson correlation matrix

between full-residue Δh profiles of each binder, enabling quantitative comparison of their allosteric signatures. Hierarchical clustering was then applied to reorder the matrix, allowing the identification of coherent groups of binders with similar allosteric behavior. This reordering revealed clusters with shared allosteric “fingerprints” (spatial distributions and magnitudes of perturbation) regardless of binder type or epitope (Figure 6A).

A tight cluster is formed by G9, G9xE5, and B3xG9 ($r > 0.98$), reflecting highly similar allosteric fingerprints driven by dimerization arm-targeting binders. These constructs modulate the ECD while variably propagating to intracellular regions depending on pairing, consistent with their intermediate activity in ERK inhibition and variable internalization profiles.

A separate, high-propagation cluster includes C1 and its derivatives (C1xE6, C1xA2, C1xB3, C1xE5), which share strong internal correlations ($r > 0.9$) and show marked propagation into JMS and kinase domains. These profiles are partially correlated with A2, G9xA2, and B3xA2 ($r \sim 0.75$ – 0.85), suggesting shared downstream communication features, though with differences in epitope engagement.

EGF_I does not cluster with EGF_III or its analogs (EGF_I \times EGF_III, cetuximab, matuzumab, E5). Rather, it falls in an intermediate position, more proximal to A2-like VHHs than to domain III-targeting binders. Meanwhile, EGF_III,

Figure 6. Global comparison of allosteric responses across EGFR binders. (A) Pearson correlation matrix of full-residue Δh profiles for all ligands, reordered by hierarchical clustering to reveal similarity in allosteric “fingerprints.” Three main clusters emerge: (i) a high-propagation group centered on C1 and its combinations (C1xE6, C1xA2, C1xB3, C1xE5); (ii) a G9-centered cluster (G9, G9xE5, B3xG9); and (iii) a weak-propagation cluster including EGF_III, cetuximab, matuzumab, E5, and E6. EGF_I does not cluster with EGF_III and occupies a more central position, partially aligned with A2-based nanobody profiles. (B) Regional average Δh values for each perturbation across eight EGFR domains: I–IV, TMH, juxtamembrane segment (JMS), and kinase C-lobe and core. C1-based combinations exhibit strong distal propagation into JMS and kinase lobes, whereas natural ligands and EGF-competitive antibodies show minimal intracellular modulation. Taken together, these two panels provide complementary views of the EGFR allosteric landscape and enable a quantitative classification of functional binder classes.

cetuximab, and E5 form a distinct cluster with weak and localized allosteric signatures, reinforcing their shared mechanism of limited perturbation. Matuzumab is more peripheral and clusters with E6 and B3xE6 ($r > 0.9$), which, despite targeting different domains, elicit similarly mild and spatially restricted responses.

This clustering captures both global similarity and mechanistic stratification: antibodies acting via EGF competition or tether stabilization form a distinct low-propagation group, while VHH-derived binders inducing conformational shifts across intracellular regions form separable, functionally richer clusters. This classification provides a quantitative foundation for dissecting mechanism-specific effects and identifying allosteric perturbations with tailored energetic fingerprints that can be compared to experimental phenotypes.

To complement the global clustering, we also averaged the Δh values over eight key structural regions of EGFR, spanning the extracellular domains (I–IV), transmembrane helix (TMH), juxtamembrane segment (JMS), and kinase module (C-lobe and core) (Figure 6B). The Δh heatmap in Figure 6B is scaled between ± 0.6 kcal/mol, corresponding to the thermal energy $k_B T$ at physiological temperature. This underlines both weak and strong allosteric effects relative to expected thermal fluctuations. The analysis highlights how different binders affect specific structural components. As expected, EGF, cetuximab, and matuzumab produced negligible effects beyond the ECD, with Δh in the kinase domain remaining close to zero (for instance, 0.03 kcal/mol for EGF_I and 0.02 kcal/mol for matuzumab). In contrast, VHHS and their combinations revealed distinct and often significant distal effects. For instance, C1xE6 and G9xE6 induced substantial Δh changes in the JMS (1.70 and 1.80 kcal/mol, respectively) and in the kinase C-lobe (1.17 and 1.26 kcal/mol), suggesting robust allosteric transmission. These effects were accompanied by important negative Δh in domain IV (-1.20 and -1.20 kcal/mol), pointing to localized rigidification as part of the long-range response. Overall, these region-level patterns support the clustering results and help identify VHH combinations, such as C1xE6 and G9xE6, as potent modulators of intracellular signaling through long-range allostery.

Experimental characterization of biparatopic VHH-based antibodies

Engineering and generation of biparatopic antibodies (BpAbs). We relied on the DuoBody[®] technology for the generation of biparatopic antibodies [40,41]. Each parental antibody was reformatted with the DuoBody[®]-specific mutations: F405L or K409R. The parental molecules were successfully expressed in Expi293F and purified. To

confirm the binding of the antibody to EGFR, a BLI experiment was conducted, which validated the binding for all parental antibodies. Controlled Fab-arm exchange (cFAE) was performed using an optimized protocol tailored for low volume and low concentration, as previously described [31]. This process resulted in the generation of all possible biparatopic constructs, culminating in a total of 12 unique combinations.

BpAbs bind EGFR in trans. Structural studies of biparatopic antibody formats suggest that these molecules often engage their targets in a *trans* configuration, where each Fab arm binds to a distinct epitope on separate EGFR molecules, rather than to two sites on the same receptor (*cis* configuration) [42]. This geometry enables receptor cross-linking, increasing the effective binding valency and enhancing overall avidity.

To experimentally characterize the binding nature of the constructs, we employed BLI. As previously described, if binding to EGFR is *trans*, the off rate (k_{off}) would be dependent on the density of antibody on the biosensor [43,44]. Consequently, we conducted a BLI assay by loading a high concentration of BpAbs (15 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) to further investigate their affinities for EGFR. Our finding revealed an increase in binding affinities, whereas the K_D could not be resolved precisely due to the low k_{off} , reinforcing the *trans* binding (see supplemental Figure S3).

Additionally, a cell-based assay using MDA-MB-468 cells, a high EGFR expressing cell line classified as triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) was conducted. Except for one construct, all other BpAbs demonstrated significant increases of cell surface saturation compared to their parental molecules, confirming their capacity to bind to EGFR in *trans* (see supplemental Figure S3).

Impact of BpAbs on EGFR signaling pathways. We next evaluated the ability of BpAbs to inhibit EGFR-mediated signaling via the MAPK/ERK and PI3K/AKT pathways (Figure 7A and D), and examined how these functional responses relate to the allosteric propagation patterns observed computationally (Figure 6). In a reporter assay for ERK pathway inhibition, most constructs demonstrated potent suppression, with IC_{50} values in the sub-nanomolar to low nanomolar range. C1xE6 (1.04×10^{-10} M) and C1xA2 (1.81×10^{-10} M) were the most effective, consistent with their strong and widespread allosteric modulation of the JMS and kinase regions identified in the Δh analysis. In contrast, B3xE6 and B3xE5 were among the least effective (IC_{50} in the micromolar range), aligning with their weak and non-cooperative Δh profiles (Figures 6 and S2, respectively).

These differences go beyond domain classification. While previous studies suggested

Figure 7. Functional characterization of parental and biparatopic anti-EGFR antibodies. (A) Inhibition of the MAPK/ERK pathway using a reporter cell line. ERK phosphorylation after EGF stimulation was measured by luminescence using a plate reader. Graph shows normalized means \pm SD. The experiment was performed three times in duplicate; data from a representative experiment are shown. (B) Inhibition of the PI3K/Akt pathway assessed by homogeneous time-resolved fluorescence (HTRF). Akt phosphorylation after EGF stimulation was quantified as the HTRF ratio: acceptor (665 nm)/donor (620 nm) \times 10,000, calculated according to the manufacturer's instructions (Revvity). Graph shows normalized means \pm SD. * $p \leq 0.05$, **** $p \leq 0.0001$. The experiment was performed three times in duplicate. (C) EGFR internalization after 4 h, determined by flow cytometry. Internalization was quantified as the loss of signal after 4 h of incubation at 37 °C compared to on ice. Graph shows normalized means \pm SD. The experiment was performed twice in duplicate; data from a representative experiment are shown. (D) Summary table of cell-based assays presented in panels A, B, and C. Values were extracted after data fitting in GraphPad prism 8. Antibodies are ranked based on protein phosphorylation (ERK and Akt) and EGFR internalization. Lower phosphorylation (indicated in blue) generally correlates with lower EGFR internalization except for cetuximab.

that antibodies targeting domain III are more effective [14], our data reveal that inhibitory potency is also shaped by epitope positioning and allosteric compatibility. For example, although A2, E5, and E6 bind overlapping regions on domain III, their biparatopic performance varied significantly when paired with G9. G9xA2 (3.13×10^{-10} M) was far more potent than G9xE5 (3.04×10^{-8} M) or G9xE6 (2.47×10^{-8} M), which matches their different capacities to modulate distal regions in the computational model. Similarly, B3xG9 was over ten times more potent than B3xE5 or B3xE6, despite all three combinations involving domain II and III binders.

Inhibition of the AKT/PI3K pathway (Figure 7B and D) followed a similar trend, with only a subset of constructs demonstrating significant activity. These included C1xB3, C1xA2, C1xE6, and G9xA2, which also showed strong allosteric propagation into the intracellular segments. Among the parental antibodies, only A2 significantly inhibited AKT phosphorylation [20],

and this property was preserved in C1xA2 and G9xA2, but not in B3xA2. These results indicate that the biparatopic format can selectively enhance, preserve, or attenuate the functional effects of its components, depending on the spatial arrangement and the strengths of the allosteric communication. The consistency between functional outcomes and predicted Δh patterns supports the utility of the SBSMMA in guiding the design of VHH combinations with tailored signaling effects.

Receptor internalization patterns and functional implications. The cross-linking of a receptor has also been shown to facilitate its internalization making BpAbs an attractive strategy for the engineering of antibody-drug conjugates (ADCs). To evaluate the impact of the biparatopic format on EGFR internalization, we conducted flow cytometry analyses. MDA-MB-468 cells were incubated with BpAbs or parental antibodies for 4 h at 37 °C to promote receptor internalization,

with a control condition maintained on ice (Figure 7C–D). After fixation, EGFR internalization was quantified by measuring the difference of fluorescence intensity between the control on ice and samples at 37 °C.

Among the parental antibodies, B3 and G9, both targeting the dimerization interface, induced the highest internalization (~47% and ~45%, respectively). However, internalization across the biparatopic constructs varied widely. B3xG9, despite combining two highly internalizing arms, did not promote significant receptor uptake, suggesting possible structural rigidity or steric hindrance at the dimerization interface when both epitopes are engaged simultaneously. Other constructs with strong signaling inhibition, such as C1xE6 and C1xA2, showed low to moderate internalization (~5–8%), aligning with their efficient distal modulation but limited capacity to promote receptor endocytosis.

This divergence emphasizes that cross-linking alone is insufficient to predict internalization, and that allosteric compatibility may play a larger role in shaping functional outcomes. Interestingly, when comparing pathway inhibition and receptor internalization (Figure 7D), an inverse correlation emerged. Finally, the constructs that promoted the highest internalization tended to be poor inhibitors of EGFR signaling, reinforcing the notion that receptor uptake and downstream signaling inhibition can be mechanistically uncoupled.

Discussion

This study provides a comprehensive view of how camelid derived sdAbs and their biparatopic combinations reshape the allosteric landscape of EGFR, and how these effects translate into distinct functional phenotypes. Our computational analysis revealed that native ligands (EGF) and therapeutic monoclonal antibodies (cetuximab, matuzumab) exert minimal long-range energetic effects when bound to the tethered EGFR monomer. In contrast, selected VHHs, such as C1 and E6, and their biparatopic combinations, induced strong allosteric modulation (Δh propagation) into the juxtamembrane segment and kinase domain. These effects were not only cooperative, but in several cases (particularly C1xE6 and C1xA2) amplified beyond the sum of their monovalent components. This distal energetic modulation proved predictive of functional inhibition: the most allosterically active combinations *in silico* were also the most potent inhibitors of MAPK and AKT signaling in cells. The weak and spatially confined allosteric profiles of cetuximab and matuzumab are also consistent with their known susceptibility to resistance, particularly to mutations affecting their domain III epitopes [45]. Since these antibodies act mainly via steric blockade and lack distal energetic

engagement, single-point mutations can abolish function, with no compensatory modulation via alternative allosteric routes. In contrast, antibodies that perturb distal regulatory nodes, such as the juxtamembrane segment or kinase domain, may retain efficacy in the presence of epitope mutations by acting through alternative, structurally coupled mechanisms.

This correlation is particularly significant given the known regulatory role of the juxtamembrane segment (JMS) and kinase C-lobe in EGFR activation. The JMS acts as a mechanical relay that links transmembrane conformational changes to the assembly of the asymmetric kinase dimer [6]. Jura and others have shown that JM-mediated dimerization is essential for catalytic activation [46], while computational structural studies of full-length EGFR in membrane environments have highlighted the centrality of the JM region in transferring extracellular inputs [34]. Nussinov and colleagues proposed a mechanistic model in which conformational changes in domain IV are transmitted via the tethering arm and JM segment to the kinase module, modulating dimerization and activation dynamics [10]. Notably, they discussed two routes of negative cooperativity in ligand binding: one via direct extracellular coupling between ligand sites, and another cascading through the tether and JMS into the intracellular domain. These insights position the JMS and C-lobe as key allosteric hubs — and our data support the idea that VHH-induced dynamics in these regions correlates with functional inhibition of EGFR signaling.

However, signaling inhibition and receptor internalization did not correlate, underscoring a key mechanistic dissociation. While B3 and G9, targeting the dimerization interface, promoted high levels of internalization (~45–47%), the B3xG9 combination failed to do so, likely due to steric constraints or conformational rigidity at the shared epitope interface. On the contrary, the strongest signaling inhibitors, C1xE6 and C1xA2, showed only modest receptor uptake (~5–8%), despite driving robust intracellular allosteric responses. These findings emphasize that cross-linking alone is not a sufficient predictor of internalization, and that epitope geometry and mechanical coupling play a central role in shaping antibody function. This decoupling of signaling and trafficking has important implications for therapeutic strategies, particularly in ADCs formats, where internalization may be desired or detrimental.

It is important to emphasize that, despite its inherent limitations — including its coarse-grained harmonic representation and thermodynamic averaging — the SBSMMA approach was able to recapitulate key aspects of VHH-induced modulation, including functional clustering, cooperativity, and biased signaling patterns. At its core, SBSMMA implements a structure-based statistical mechanical framework in which the

protein is modeled as a harmonic network, and allosteric communication is computed as the propagation of free energy perturbations across the structure. While this simplicity necessarily precludes atomic-level resolution or explicit dynamics, it offers major advantages in computational speed and interpretability, enabling systematic evaluation of large antibody panels. When paired with structural predictions – such as from AlphaFold3 – the SBSMMA thus provides a highly tractable and mechanistically grounded tool for mapping the allosteric landscape of complex targets such as EGFR.

More broadly, our findings support a conceptual shift: allostery is not exclusive to small-molecule pharmacology. The same principles of distal energetic communication apply to biologics, including sdAbs, multispecifics [47], and de novo-designed binders [6]. In this light, antibodies are not simply occupancy-based blockers, but mechanical perturbators capable of rewiring signaling by engaging structurally privileged, allosterically sensitive epitopes.

With the rise of AI-driven structure prediction, epitope mapping, and generative protein design, the opportunity now exists to rationally design antibodies that not only bind with high affinity, but exert targeted allosteric effects on the target protein [48–50]. Our work demonstrates that computational allosteric analysis can guide this design process, predicting functional outcomes based on the location and compatibility of epitopes.

To conclude, we show that epitope identity, spatial arrangement, and energetic compatibility define the performance of single and biparatopic EGFR-targeting antibodies. These insights support a rational, mechanism-based framework for designing next-generation biologics with tunable signaling, trafficking, and therapeutic profiles.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Léxane Fournier: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Stefan Becker:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Stefan Zielonka:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Enrico Guarnera:** Writing – original draft, Visualization, Supervision, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

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DATA AVAILABILITY

We shared the link to figshare for predicted 3D VHH-EGFR complexes.

DECLARATION OF COMPETING INTEREST

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: 'Léxane Fournier, Stefan Becker, Stefan Zielonka, and Enrico Guarnera are employees of Merck Healthcare KGaA.'

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

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